

**Modelling input and output price changes to
Scottish Agriculture, using the ScotFarm Model**

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Executive summary

In 2022, the annual average price in the UK increased by up to 20.0% for agricultural outputs and 27.7% for agricultural inputs compared with the annual average prices in 2021 (DEFRA, 2023). These recent and potentially future price changes are likely to have impacts on Scottish agricultural system. Understanding the impacts of these changes on farm economy and production is important to minimise economic and production consequences on Scottish agricultural system. This analysis explored the impact of current price inflation on four most common farming systems in Scotland – Dairy, Beef, Sheep and Arable – using a farm level optimising model, ScotFarm. Two alternative price scenarios were examined; a price inflation scenario that used current price inflation (scenario PI2025) and a hypothetical scenario that ignores the current price inflation and maintains historical trend of price change before 2020 price increase (scenario FAPRI2025). The model outputs of farm net profit and production levels in 2025 were compared with that in 2020 in this analysis.

The results showed that an increase in milk price had a small but positive impact on dairy farming system with an estimation of 5% increase in farm net profit on an average dairy farm (Figure 1). Dairy farms were projected to have fared slightly better under price inflation compared to when no price inflation was assumed. These farms did not change their production level under both alternative price scenarios. The Scottish beef farming system were projected to have had a small but negative impact due to price inflation. An average beef farm was estimated to have around 5% reduction in farm net profit. There was a reduction in production of around 6% on an average beef farm. The counterfactual scenario results suggested that beef farms would have benefitted if there were no price inflation with 3% increase in farm net profit.

Sheep and arable farming systems were estimated to have a substantial reduction in farm net margin under the price inflation scenario. An average sheep farm would have a reduction of almost 30% in farm net profit under the price inflation scenario. The production on this farm was projected to reduce by 17%. Like dairy and beef farms, sheep farms would, however, had benefitted if there were no price inflation in the market. These farms would have seen a small but positive increase in farm net profit with no changes in farm production levels.

Figure 1: Percentage change in farm net profit for four farming systems under alternative price scenarios compared to the Base year 2020

For an average arable farm, the net profit was estimated to reduce by 26% under the price inflation scenario. Cereal production on farm was expected to reduce by up to 12%. However, oil seed rape production on farms was projected to increase slightly by 4%. The arable farms were projected to have a very small loss in farm net profit (-3%) if there were no price inflation assumed with no production changes on farms.

Introduction

This report presents an analysis of the impacts of current agricultural price inflation on Scottish farming systems in response to a call-down request from the Scottish Government. It used a farm level optimising model, ScotFarm¹ and Scottish Farm Business Survey (Scottish Government, 2020) farm level data to conduct the analysis. The model maximises farm net profit under the optimum use of farm resources such as land, labour and other inputs. Four most common Scottish farming systems; dairy, beef, sheep and arable farming systems were identified from the FBS dataset and used for this analysis. Two alternative price scenarios were analysed: i) a Price Inflation scenario (PI2025) and ii) a Counterfactual baseline price scenario (FAPRI2025). The ScotFarm model is a dynamic farm economic model and runs for a 15-year (2016 to 2030) modelling period. It provides annual farm net profit for a base year 2020 (average of 2019, 2020 and 2021) and simulation year 2025 (average of 2024, 2025 and 2026). Farm net profit is taken as a measure where farm net profit in the simulation year 2025 was compared with the farm net profit in the base year 2020 model to determine the impacts of price scenarios. This report presents the modelling results in two parts; i) inter-farm comparison and ii) intra-farm comparison to capture variability of impacts between different farming systems and within the same farming system.

Methodology

ScotFarm

The ScotFarm model² maximises farm net profit allowing optimal use of resources within a farm. The model is based on farming system analysis where a holistic approach is used to represent bio-economic activities on a farm. The farm net profit is estimated by determining **accumulated revenues and farm support payments minus production related variable costs and farm overheads**. The livestock production variable costs include **veterinary, medicine, haulage and other miscellaneous livestock production costs**. The arable crop production variable costs include **costs of spray, fertiliser, seed, haulage, irrigation and other miscellaneous crop production costs**. The overhead costs in the model

¹ For details see [ScotFarm - a farm level optimising model – SRUC, Scotland's Rural College](#)

² For details visit [ScotFarmManual.pdf \(sruc.ac.uk\)](#)

includes fuel, electricity, machinery depreciation and repairs, rents, interests and insurance costs. ScotFarm is a dynamic model, runs and maximises farm net profit over a 15-year time frame. The farm activities are constraint over farm resources such as land, feed, replacement stocks and labour. There are two sets of model inputs used; the Farm Business Survey, FBS 2020 where starting farm variables (such as herd size and land use) and farm parameters (such as calving rate and stocking rate) are derived. The second set of inputs are the price indices taken from FAPRI-UK model results (AFBI, 2020). The farm level data were drawn from the FBS for 4 different farming systems: Dairy, Beef, Sheep and Arable farming systems.

For this analysis, three-year averaged output was used to minimise initial and terminal biasness of linear programming technique. Hence, the output for the base year 2020 is the averaged output of 2019, 2020 and 2021 and the output of the simulation year 2025 output is the averaged output of 2024, 2025 and 2026.

Scenarios

Price Inflation scenario (PI2025)

The Price Inflation scenario (PI2025) used the current price increase for agricultural outputs and inputs based on published UK agricultural price index (DEFRA, 2023). Table 1 shows the changes in the output and input prices of different agricultural commodities in 2022 compared to 2021. There is substantial increase in output prices for barley, oats and oilseed rape and input prices for fuel and fertiliser. The ScotFarm model used first seven-year prices (from 2016 to 2022) based on the real market price (DEFRA, 2023). From the year 2023 to the year 2030, the prices were projected under an assumption that the current inflation would be maintained over that period.

Table 1: Changes in price for different agricultural commodities in 2022 compared to 2021.

	price change
Outputs	
Wheat	25%
Barley	44%
Oats	40%
Oilseed Rape	47%
Cattle	8%
Sheep	4%
Milk	21%

Inputs	
Feed	11%
Seeds	9%
Fuel	40%
Fertilizer	70%
Veterinary	1%
Interest rate	4%

The annual variability in prices were maintained based on the baseline price projections estimated by the sector model FAPRI (AFBI, 2020). The price changes for different outputs and inputs indexed to 2018 prices are presented in Figure 2. This scenario assumed an additional interest rate (4%) included to the farm overheads over the price inflation modelling period (2022 -2030).

Figure 2: Price indices for different agriculture commodities under the PI2025 scenario

Counterfactual baseline price scenario (FAPRI2025)

The counterfactual baseline scenario (FAPRI2025) assumed a pre-2020 historic price trend over the model timeframe. It retains the market price from 2016 to 2018 same as under the PI2025 scenario. From the year 2019 onwards, price projections were based on price change estimated by FAPRI model under its post-Brexit Free Trade Agreement scenario (AFBI, 2020). The price change under this scenario is presented in Figure 3. This scenario represented a hypothetical market condition if current price shock in 2021/22 had not occurred.

Figure 3: Price indices under the FARPI2025 scenario

Results

Inter-farm variability

The price inflation was projected to have different impacts in different farming systems (Figure 4). Dairy farms were estimated to improve their profits slightly (+5%) under PI2025 scenario compared to the base year 2020. Although milk price increased by 21% under this scenario, it was counteracted by an increase in feed costs and other livestock variable costs. Farms in all other three farming systems; beef, sheep and arable farms were projected to have reductions in farm net profits. Beef farms were estimated to have 5% reduction on net profit under the price inflation scenario. This suggests that the price increase in beef outputs were not sufficient to counteract price increase in beef inputs. Sheep farms were projected to have substantial reduction (-29%) in farm net profits. Sheep output price increase under the price inflation scenario was modest compared to the increase in input prices for sheep farms resulting in a larger reduction in profits. Scottish arable farming system (represented here by the specialist cereal farms) were also expected to have a substantial reduction in their net profits. The cereal prices increased between 25% to 47% for different crops but higher increase in input prices (such as 70% increase in fertilizer and 40% increase in fuel costs) had a larger negative impact on farms and reduced their net profits substantially.

Figure 4: Changes in farm net profit for different farming systems in the base year and scenarios

The farm net profit estimated under the hypothetical FAPRI2025 showed little change from the farm net profit in base year 2020 for all the farming systems (Figure 4). It shows that farms in all three farming systems; beef, sheep and arable farms would have fared better if price inflation had not happened. The sheep and arable farms were estimated to have 44% and 31% higher net profit under the FAPRI2025 scenario compared to the PI2025 scenario (Figure 4). However, dairy farms were estimated to have small reduction of 3% when no-price inflation was assumed compared to the price inflation scenario.

Intra-farm variability

Dairy

The average farm net profit for a dairy farm was estimated to be £89,042 per year in 2020. However, there was some degree of variability between dairy farms based on farm net profit (Figure 5). Figure 5 shows the farm net profits of individual farms, ranked in ascending order from left to right based on their net profits under the PI2025 scenario. Top performing farms were estimated to generate a net profit more than £200,000 per year on average whereas there were few dairy farms who were estimated making losses.

Figure 5: Farm net profits in the base year 2020 and under alternative price scenarios for individual dairy farms (farms are ranked in ascending order based on net profit in the PI2025)

The results showed that the impact of price inflation on farm net profit followed the profit curve in the base year 2020. The impact of price inflation was negative in lower profit farms as it further reduced their farm net profits. On the other hand, price inflation had beneficial impact on farm profit for the farms in the higher end of profitability. The results also showed that farm net profit for most farms would have stayed the same if there was no price inflation. Nevertheless, few farms were estimated to benefit under the FAPRI2025 scenario.

The farm variability of the impacts of the price scenarios is further illustrated in Figure 6. Here the median of the farm profit slightly reduced under the PI2025 scenario compared to the Base year 2020 and FAPRI2025 scenarios. The upper quartile of the range however, moved up increasing the range and spread of the farm net profit of individual farms compared to the Base year 2020. This suggested that there was a variability of impact of PI2025 scenario on individual farms where farms in the upper quartile benefitted more from increased milk price compared to other farms.

Figure 6: A box whisker plot presenting dairy farm net profit in the base year 2020 and under the alternative price scenarios.

Beef

The Scottish beef farms were estimated to have an average £ 30,505 of farm net profit per farm in 2020. Around 30% of farms, however, were making loss in 2020 (Figure 7). There was only a very small variability in the impact of price inflation on beef farm net margins. Few of the loss-making beef farms had a large reduction to their farm net profit under the PI2025 scenario whereas most profitable beef farms showed a slight increase in their farm net profits.

Figure 7: Farm net profits in the base year 2020 and under alternative price scenarios for individual beef farms (farms are ranked in ascending order based on net profit in the PI2025)

There was not much change in the range and spread of individual farm net profit under the PI2025 scenario compared to the Base year 2020 scenario (Figure 8). It suggested that the impact of price inflation on beef farms was almost homogenous and followed the profitability levels of individual farms in the base year. Under FAPRI2025, the beef farms showed a reduced variability from the Base year 2020 with farms in the lower quartile of farm net profit moving upwards reducing the spread of individual farm net profit. This suggested that farms with lower profitability benefitting more when price change was assumed to stay with the historical trend. However, this variability was not statistically significant between farms.

Figure 8: A box and whisker plot showing the farm net margin in the base year 2020 and under the alternative price scenarios.

Sheep

The annual farm net profit was estimated to be £ 19,657 on average for a sheep farm in the base year 2020. Only one fifth of sheep farms showed positive impact of price inflation (Figure 9). But most sheep farms (80%) were projected to have reduction in farm net margin under the PI2025 scenario. Farm net profit under the

FAPRI2025 scenario was estimated to be like the farm profits in the base year 2020 for all farms.

Figure 9: Farm net profits in the base year 2020 and under alternative price scenarios for individual sheep farms (farms are ranked in ascending order based on net profit in the PI2025)

There was a high variability of the impact of price inflation on sheep farms. The spread of individual farm net profits increased in both top and lower quartiles under the PI2025 as shown in Figure 10. The median and lower quartile showed a substantial reduction in farm net profits compared to those in the base year 2020 suggesting that price inflation had higher consequences on farm economy on farms with lower profitability. Farms, under the no price inflation scenario (FAPRI2025), were estimated to have net farm profits very similar to the base year 2020. There was a slight increase in profits of an average farm as well as farms in the lower quartile of profitability.

Figure 10: A box whisker plot presenting farm net profit for sheep farms in the base year 2020 and under the alternative price scenarios

Arable

The arable farming system was represented by the specialist cereals farms in this study. The average farm net profit in 2020² for these farms was estimated to be £34,622 per farm. These farms showed a substantial variability of the impact of price inflation on individual arable farms (Figure 11). More than half of the farms had a reduction in farm net profit under the PI2025 scenario. The extent of impact of price inflation ranged from +£3000 to -£160,000 on these arable farms.

Figure 11: Farm net profits in the base year 2020 and under alternative price scenarios for individual arable farms (farms are ranked in ascending order based on net profit in the PI2025)

There were also some changes in farm net profit under the no price inflation (FAPRI2025) scenario, but the impact of the scenario was less pronounced than that of price inflation scenario (PI2025).

There was a larger spread of farms under the PI2025 scenario especially at the lower quartile (Figure 12). This suggested that the negative impact of price inflation was higher for the farms with lower profitability. The spread of farm profits under the FAPRI2025 became narrower than that under the PI2025 scenario with higher farm profits estimated on farms within the lower quartile. Higher median and average values of farm net profits compared to the PI2025 scenario also indicated that an average arable farm would have benefited if there was no price inflation scenario as indicated by

Figure 12: A box whisker plot presenting farm net profit for arable farms in the base year 2020 and under the alternative price scenarios

Farm production level

The dairy farms were not projected to have any changes in their milk production levels under the PI2025 scenario (Figure 13). There was, however, some changes estimated for other three farming systems. The sheep and beef farming systems were estimated to reduce their production levels; -17% on an average sheep farm and -6% on an average beef farm. In arable farming system, all cereal production were estimated to decrease by around 11%. However, oil seed rape (OSR) production in some of the arable farms was projected to increase by 4%.

Figure 13: Percentage changes in farm production level for different farming systems under the PI2025 scenario compared to the Base year 2020 scenario

Conclusions

The recent price inflation in agriculture sector in the UK is estimated to have substantial variability in impact on different Scottish farming systems. The dairy farming system show a small but positive impact of price inflation whereas all other three farming systems; beef, sheep and arable systems, are expected to have economic consequences of increased prices. Dairy farms are the most profitable and considered to be more efficient in production than any other farming systems in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2023) and hence are expected to minimise the negative impact of increased input prices as well as to benefit from increased milk price. Beef farms are projected to have a small negative impact of price inflation, but sheep and arable farming systems are estimated to have a substantial reduction in farm net profit. Increase in sheep price is relatively smaller compared to an increase in input prices and hence, sheep farms are estimated to have a substantial reduction in their farm net profits. Regarding arable farms, a large increase in input prices especially in fertilizer and fuel prices is the main reason for the expected reduction in farm net profit. The results also suggest that these farms would have benefitted if there were no current price hike in the UK market and if the agricultural prices had maintained the pre-2020 price trends. There is some variability of the impact of price inflation between different farms within a farming system. It is observed that lower profit-making farms show larger negative impact of price increase whereas higher profit-making farms benefited from price increases. This is true for farms in all four farming systems which suggests that, in general, farms with higher profitability show higher resilience to higher input prices and can exploit improved output prices.

Although a dynamic model in nature, ScotFarm does not have a feedback response of changes in market supply. The model runs on an assumption that the 2022/23 price increase in agricultural outputs and inputs will be maintained for next 7 to 8 years. This study tried to minimise these limitations by using price indices generated by a sector model, FAPRI which accounts for market and production feedbacks. We found that there is a 10%–20% difference in different agriculture price indices between the current market price indices (DEFRA, 2023) and model projected price indices used in this study. Bearing in mind the high degree of uncertainty associated with market prices, it should be noted that the model results presented in this report are the estimated projections not the exact predictions of the changes in Scottish farming systems under future price inflation.

References

AFBI, 2020. Impact on UK Agriculture of changes to Direct Payments following Brexit. <https://www.afbini.gov.uk/publications/impact-uk-agriculture-changes-direct-payments-following-brexit>

DEFRA, 2023. Agricultural price indices – United Kingdom: February 2023. <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/agricultural-price-indices/agricultural-price-indices-united-kingdom-february-2023>

Scottish Government, 2021. Scottish farm business income: annual estimates 2020–2021. <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-farm-business-income-annual-estimates-2020-2021/documents/>

Scottish Government, 2023. Scottish farm business income: annual estimates 2021–2022. <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-farm-business-income-annual-estimates-2021-2022/>

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